

ON SMARANDACHE SIMPLE CONTINUED FRACTIONS

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Abstract. Let $A = \{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a Smarandache type sequence. In this paper we show that if A is a positive integer sequence, then the simple continued fraction $[a_1, a_2, \dots]$ is convergent.

Let $A = \{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a Smarandache type sequence. Then The simple continued frction

$$(1) \quad a_1 + \frac{1}{a_2 + \frac{1}{a_3 + \frac{1}{\dots}}}$$

is called the Smarandache simple continued fraction associated A (See [1]). By the usually symbol (see [2, Notion 10.1]), the continued frction (1) can be written as $[a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots]$. Recently, Castillo [1] posed the following question:

Question. Is the continued fraction (1) convergent? In particular, is the continued fraction $[1, 12, 123, \dots]$ convergent?

In this paper we give a positive answer as follows.

Theorem. If A is a positive integer sequence, then the

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continued fraction (1) is convergent.

Proof. If A is a positive integer sequence, then (1) is a usually simple continued fraction and its quotient are positive integers. Therefore, by [2, Theorem 165], it is convergent. The Theorem is proved.

On applying [2, Theorems 165 and 176], we get a further result immediately.

Theorem 2. If A is an infinite positive integer sequence, then (1) is equal to an irrational number α . Further, if A is not periodic, then α is not an algebraic number of degree two.

References

1. J.Castillo, Smarandache continued fractions, Smarandache Notions J., to appear. Vol. 9, No. 1-2, 40-42, 1998.
2. G.H.Hardy and E.M.Wright, An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers, Oxford Univ. Press, Oxford, 1938.